

Supporting Information

Title

Label-Free detection of biochemical changes during cortical organoids maturation via Raman spectroscopy and Machine Learning

Authors

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Figure S1 A schematic of the multimodal Raman microscope

Class	Precision	Recall	F1-score
6 W	99.78 ± 0.3	98.3 ± 0.7	99.0 ± 0.4
12 W	97.87 ± 0.7	97.3 ± 0.9	97.6 ± 0.5
16 W	87 ± 1	93 ± 1	90.1 ± 0.8
20 W	93 ± 1	89 ± 1	91 ± 1

Table S2 Summary of classification metrics for Random Forest model performance. The table includes recall, precision, F1-score, and accuracy values for each class, along with their standard deviations across 30 cross-validation trials

Figure S2 Minimum detectable time intervals during PGP1- cortical organoid maturation. (A) Pairwise comparison of Euclidean distances between developmental stages, with the smallest separable group (16-20 months) identified at a threshold of 0.85. (B) Euclidean distances between group centroids in the PCA space for PC1, PC2, and PC4, highlighting separability between maturation stages (6, 12, 16, and 20 weeks). (C-D) Estimated minimum detectable differences for earlier intervals. Groups between 6 and 12 weeks correspond to a minimum detectable interval of 1 week, and between 12 and 16 weeks, 0.5 weeks.

Figure S3 Random Forest model for classification of H1 derived organoid maturation stages and biomarkers extraction H1-derived organoid. (A) Confusion matrix and a table showing Precision, Recall and F1-score of the predicted class illustrating the performance of the model (B) Bar plot of the PCs coefficient importance extracted from RF across the first 25 principal components. (C) Plot of the loadings as function of Raman shift of the most important PCs, namely PC1, PC2 and PC5. (D) Box plots of select peak intensities in the dataset based on the ability to discriminate maturation stages (500 binned spectra collected from three independent organoids). Significance denoted by an asterisk (*), was determined at $p < 0.05$.